

METHODS OF WORKING WITH EXERCISES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In this article, an attempt was made to provide scientific information on the topic of exercise-related techniques in teaching a foreign language.*

Keywords: *non-speech exercises, phonetic, grammatic and lexical exercises, creative speech exercises.*

МЕТОДЫ РАБОТЫ С УПРАЖНЕНИЯМИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В данной статье предпринята попытка представить научную информацию по теме упражнений, связанных с приемами обучения иностранному языку.*

Ключевые слова: *неречевые упражнения, фонетические, грамматические и лексические упражнения, творческие речевые упражнения.*

The results of teaching a foreign language are determined primarily through the exercise system, since the practical goal in learning a foreign language is that the acquisition of all types of speech activity is carried out using exercises.

So what are the exercises? Exercise refers to operations or actions that are performed individually or sequentially, aimed at acquiring a certain activity or to improve that activity in educational situations. The requirement for exercises is that they must be adequate to the qualifications and skills being formed. If the exercises intended for training do not have a speech character, the skills and abilities that are formed will not have a communicative character.

That is why the speech skill should be formed only on the basis of speech situations in speech activity. Hence, it is necessary that speech skills and competencies are formed not in language exercises, but in speech-oriented exercises that reflect or are close to this speech—that is, communicative activity. In the methodological literature, we can see different classifications of exercises. It is based on different principles. According to the principle of communicativity, we can distinguish between three types of exercises:

1. Non-speech exercises.

2. Exercises for speech-oriented training: a) phonetic, grammatical and lexical exercises according to the aspects of the language. b) exercises in the creative movement.

3. Real speech exercises.

The most important role in the formation of skills is considered to be speech-oriented exercises, being one of the exercises. And real speech exercises help to form speech skills in all types of speech activity. Non-speech exercises are divided into two: language exercises and pre-speech exercises.

Language exercises are on aspects and are aimed at studying language phenomena. To form a whole sentence from fragments (words), to form a sentence according to the rule, to change the structure of the sentence on the basis of its transformation and x. k. Now we will

consider exercises aimed at forming language and speech skills. Of the most common types of exercise, the following are currently considered:

1. Training or exercises intended for training or training.

2. Creative speech exercises. The first includes language exercises (lexical, phonetic, grammatical). Their characteristic feature is that in this, speech skills are focused not on dressing, but on the study of the form of language phenomena. So they cannot be speech exercises because they cannot raise the use of language material by students to an automated level. All preparatory exercises aimed at training language units outside of speech activity, automation are called pre-speech exercises. These include exercises based on displacement and imitation. Speech exercises. They are divided into pure speech exercises and speech-oriented exercises. They are considered training speech exercises and exercises aimed at aspects (that is, phonetic, grammatical, lexical.). Non-speech exercises. Pre - speech exercises.

Purpose:

1) separate automation of language phenomena in addition to speech activity.

2) analytical exercises consisting of language exercises (receptive, reproductive) sentence structure according to the intended purpose and rule, analysis of language phenomena, transformation.

Of the greatest importance in the formation of speech skills is considered to be exercises aimed at speech. They are exercises that have a training harakter. Such exercises take into account, on the one hand, the specific elements of the type of speech activity being studied, and on the other hand, the aspects of language material that are difficult for students. Since the process of teaching a foreign language is artificially formed, despite having a comunicative orientation, it would be wrong to say that it is based on purely informative motivation. Therefore, even under artificial conditions, it is not correct to call exercises purely comunicative exercises. As a result, some methodologists deny their use in educational proceedings. The reason is that they insist that they are not informative. Others, having limited themselves to pure speech exercises for a long time, forget that they have not only speech activity, but also a training, training harakter. Not only is it a means of teaching reading, it is also a means of teaching other types of speech activity (that is, oral speech and writing).

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